

MATERIALS SCIENCE AND MECHANICS OF MACHINES

REAL-TIME STUDY OF COCOONS OF SILKWORM SHADE

Korabelnikov A.,

*Ph.D, associate Professor of the Department of Silk Technology,
Tashkent Institute of Textile and Light Industry, Republic of Uzbekistan*

Mirzakhodjayev B.,

*D.Sc., senior researcher Sericulture Mechanization Laboratory,
Scientific-research Institute of Sericulture
c. Tashkent, Republic of Uzbekistan*

Abdurahmanova M.

*assistant of the Department of Silk Technology,
Tashkent Institute of Textile and Light Industry*

Radjabov I.

doctoral of Research Institute of Sericulture

Abstract

In order to produce high-grade raw silk, it is necessary to sort the cocoons according to the shade of the shell color. Visually, the white cocoon shells of the Mayin Tola-1 and Mayin Tola-2 hybrids turned out to be about 67.9-46.2% purple, 2.06-15.4% yellow, 23.0-30.2% cream and 6.5-7.5% yellow-brown shades, respectively, under ultraviolet irradiation. Cocoons with a purple shade of the shell had the highest technological indicators. With the help of dyeing, it is shown that silk produced from raw materials of the same shade, established with the help of ultraviolet transmission, received a uniform color, and the control, consisting of raw materials of various shades, was dyed with a defect, unevenly. It has been established that for the production of smooth-dyed silk fabrics of delicate tones, it is necessary to use raw silk as a raw material, produced from cocoons with the same shade of shell color.

Keywords: silkworm cocoons, shell, shade, sorting, technological properties of the thread, device, ultraviolet transmission.

INTRODUCTION

A cocoon is a protective shell created by a silkworm caterpillar before turning it into a pupa. The quality and economic value of cocoons are characterized by: external signs, physical, mechanical and technological properties of their shells and threads.

Cocoons are distinguished by color: pure white, white with shades, yellow of various shades, green with shades, cream and pink. The most common cocoons are white (the natural color of fibroin with a transparent sericin layer and partially yellow. The color is given to cocoons by substances that stain the sericin layer [1]. The shades of cocoons are determined by luminescent analysis under ultraviolet rays. Under the action of ultraviolet rays, cocoon shells of various colors and shades glow differently: white – blue-purple; yellow and golden-yellow - yellow-brown; cream and fawn — purple-brown and yellow; green - bright yellow and yellow-purple. The coloration and shade of cocoons within the same breed vary greatly.

It has been established that in order to produce high-grade raw silk, it is necessary to sort cocoons according to the shade of the shell color. With the help of dyeing, it was revealed that silk produced from raw materials of the same shade, established with the help of ultraviolet transmission, received a uniform color. It has been established that for the production of smooth-dyed silk fabrics of delicate tones, it is necessary to use raw silk produced from cocoons with the same shade of shell color as a raw material [2,3].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the existing state standard for sorting live and dry cocoons, there are a number of disadvantages, firstly, cocoons are sorted manually, by visual method. At the end of sorting, about 2% of the waste is in the cocoon batch, which affects the unwinding and quality of raw silk. We offer two sorting methods: by the whiteness of the cocoons and by the defect of the shell.

Sorting cocoons by whiteness will reduce the time-consuming process of sorting and evaluating the quality of cocoons.

To solve this problem, you can use a digital camera or a photo sensor with a computer program.

For this purpose, we chose a tape feed of cocoons one at a time, while the colors of the cocoons are quickly and efficiently determined [4].

For the second method, we used a computer program to recognize the brightness, color, and whiteness of the silk shell [5]. With the help of the program, a snapshot of the object is taken and the whiteness level is compared with the values entered in advance, if the color matches the value in the database, then the color is white, if it fits partially, then it is white, but with spots, etc.

The use of a photodetector is "classic", it is more time-consuming (all photometer-type devices that determine whiteness are made on the basis of a photodiode and a xenon flash, it has several photodiodes that

are located at different degrees, which: fix the brightness - refraction of the beam flux, then output the average brightness flux.

Disadvantage: the photodiode will need to be calibrated to 100% light every 5 hours, which takes time within 4-5 minutes (this calibration should be done on all photometers).

The device we offer is connected to the COM1 port after downloading the program for analysis (the program converts the received signals into FLOAT-type digits for software analysis), an LPT command bridge is connected for the motion sensor, for stopping and starting the belt conveyor.

The program uses ultraviolet rays, since silk is easier to analyze under ultraviolet light.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For the project and the program, a belt (conveyor) feed was chosen, since in calculations this system is the most manageable and more acceptable (also cheap). If the cocoon feeding system is conveyor, that is, tape feeding of cocoons, the reading system can be carried out by a digital camera or a photo sensor. Let's consider several options, Figure 1 shows the ribbon feeding of cocoons.

Figure 1. Ribbon feeding of cocoons.

As shown in Figure 1, the cocoon follows a ribbon feed, where there are light bulbs on both edges, which will not allow the cocoon to fall during movement. The following blocks T and R are motion sensors that record the exact location for the "control point", here T is

an infrared diode transmitter, R is a photodiode, the speed of the tape is adjustable. Below are two options for solving the checkpoint. Figure 2 shows a whiteness control system using photo and light diodes.

Figure 2. Scheme of photo light-diode control

In order to achieve the most accurate result, it is best to place a control point over the tape feed, this will protect against the ingress of other extraneous rays.

The motion sensor can be positioned at the edges. F- photo sensor, L-LED the control point is located above the beginning of the motion sensor, which will accurately fix and determine the whiteness of the ob-

ject. Ultraviolet light comes from the L-LED to a moving object, thereby refracting the luminous flux onto the photodiode, which will give a more accurate central definition. L and F are arranged in such a way that gives an accurate refraction of the light flux directly onto the photodiode. Figure 3 shows a diagram using a digital camera.

Figure 3. A diagram using a digital camera.

The use of a digital camera, as seen in Figure 3, can be used as a whiteness recognizer. If you set up the luminous flux correctly, then you can control the whiteness according to a template (preset in a computer program) to pass through the system at a speed of 1 second, that is, 60 cocoons in 1 minute. The analysis does not require a high-precision image, it can be blurry, so you

Figure 4. Device for determining the shade of the cocoon shell

The shade of cocoons of new silkworm hybrids was studied on the device. Table 1. shows the results of luminescent analysis of cocoons by various shades of the Mayin Tola-1 and Mayin Tola-2 rocks.

can only determine the whiteness, and not the geometric structure of the object.

Based on the above schemes, a program for sorting cocoons in real time has been developed [5] and an automated device for sorting cocoons [6], as well as a device for determining the shade of the cocoon shell. Fig. 4.

Based on the proposed schemes and computer programs, a device for sorting cocoons based on MKK-1 equipment was developed and a patent of the Republic of Uzbekistan was obtained.

Table 1.

Results of luminescent analysis of cocoons

Cocoon Hybrid	Color of the analyzed cocoons	Percentage of cocoons glowing in ultraviolet rays			
		Purple $x \pm T_x$	Golden yellow $x \pm T_x$	Cream $x \pm T_x$	Yellow-brown $x \pm T_x$
Mayin Tola-1	Белый	67,9±2,85	2,06±0,13	23,0±1,19	6,5±0,26
Mayin Tola-2	Белый	46,19±2,04	15,45±0,77	30,25±1,5	7,5±0,315

As can be seen from the table, visually, the white shells of cocoons of the hybrid Mayin Tola-1 and Mayin Tola-2 with ultraviolet transmission turned out to be about 67,9-46,2% purple, 2,06-15,4% yellow, 23,0-30,2% cream and 6,5-7,5% yellow-brown shades, respectively.

Next, the cocoons with a purple shade were unwound on a cocoon winding machine, the results of a single unwinding of cocoons with a purple shade are shown in Table 2.

Table 2.

Results of single unwinding of cocoons with a purple shade

№	Indicators	Hybrids	
		Mayin tola-1	Mayin tola-2
1	The amount of unwound raw silk, %	42,78±2	44,86±2
2	Scraps, %	5,9±2	5,48±2
3	Membrane, %	3,70±0,33	2,8±0,11
4	Pupa, %	45,0±0,58	44,2±55
5	Quantity of silk fiber, %	51,29±0,21	52,2±0,21
6	Unwinding of the shell, %	82,12±0,56	83,7±0,32
7	Specific consumption of cocoons, кг	2,6±0,5	2,5±0,5
8	Total length of filament, m	1170	1250
9	Continuously unwound thread length, м	720	875
10	Line density of cocoon thread, tex	0,263±0,004	0,261±0,005
11	Coefficient of variation in the linear density of the cocoon thread, %	25,4±0,09	18,2±0,003
	Cocoon shell	18,7±0,30	14,5±0,25
	Between cocoons	6,9	3,3
	Total	23,5	11,9

The data in Table 2 indicate that the new hybrids are characterized by good technological properties. Attention is drawn to the high metric numbers of hybrids Mayin tola-1 – 0,263 tex, Mayin tola-2 – 0,261 tex, the total length of the thread of hybrids Mayin tola-1 – 1170 m, Mayin tola-2 – 1250 m. and the high yield of raw silk Mayin tola-1 is 42,78%, Mayin tola-2 is 44,86%. Such high technological indicators once again testify to the benefits of introducing cocoon sorting according to the shade of the shell color in industrial sericulture.

CONCLUSIONS

1. It has been established that in order to produce high-grade raw silk, it is necessary to sort cocoons on an automated conveyor according to the shade of the shell color.

2. Visually, the white cocoon shells of the Mayin Tola-1 and Mayin Tola-2 hybrid turned out to be about 67,9-46,2% purple, 2,06-15,4% yellow, 23,0-30,2% cream and 6,5-7,5% yellow-brown shades, respectively, under ultraviolet irradiation.

3. The highest technological indicators were for cocoons with a purple tinge of the shell: metric numbers of hybrids Mayin tola-1 – 0,263 tex, Mayin tola-2 – 0,261 tex, the total length of the thread of hybrids Mayin tola-1 – 1170 m, Mayin tola-2 – 1250 m. and the high yield of raw silk Mayin tola-1 – 42,78%, Mayin tola-2 – 44,86%.

3. With the help of dyeing, it was found that silk produced from raw materials of the same shade, se-

lected using ultraviolet transmission, received a uniform color, and consisting of raw materials of various shades, dyed with a defect, unevenly.

4. It has been established that for the production of smooth-dyed silk fabrics of delicate tones, it is necessary to use raw silk, produced from cocoons with the same shade of shell color, as a raw material.

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